

Supplementary Material: Financial credit risk measurement using a binary classification model.

APPENDIX 2: Input and output variables.

Input variables

Family responsibilities: it is the number of people who depend economically on the debtor.

Destination of the Credit: for what the delivered capital will be used.

Age: is the number of years of the debtor.

Marital Status: marital status of the person.

Gender: Defined gender of the client.

Guarantee: it is the guarantee offered by the debtor to the financial institution.

Amount: consists of the initial value of money granted to the client as a loan.

Instruction Level: client education instruction level. The options are without studies, school, college or university.

Institutional Loans: if the client has loans in other institutions

Number of credits: it is the number of credits that the client has or has had with the entity.

Type of credit: type of credit you are requesting. The options are for consumption, mortgage or microcredit.

Type of Housing: is the type of housing in which the debtor lives.

Income: is the amount of monthly income for work activities.

Expenses: monthly reduction of the client's income.

Assets: the sum of all assets owned by the customer.

Liabilities: total amount of debts now.

Interest Rate: the percentage of use of the borrowed money.

Seniority of the client in the institution: it is the number of credits that the client has or has had with the financial entity.

Work seniority: it is the time that the debtor has in his current job.

Geographical area: place where the client lives. The options are urban and rural.

Number of payments: the credit term.

Payment Frequency: frequency established to pay.

Economic Activity: work activity of the person.

Amount of each payment: value of each payment according to the established frequency.

Payment capacity: evaluates the customer's monthly payment capacity.

Customer type: The options are new or recurring.

Customer Rating: This is the latest risk rating based on the customer's credit payment behavior.

Output variable.

The output variable is the result of the prediction.